

INCLUSIVE CULTURE AS A PEDAGOGICAL DIMENSION OF SUCCESSFUL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15093429>

***Annotaton.** This article discusses inclusive education and the development of an inclusive culture in society. The article reiterates the importance of inclusive education extending inclusion to every section of society, meeting the unique needs of each individual, and seeing significant changes in society. Methods and practices used to develop an inclusive culture are discussed as well.*

***Key words:** inclusive education, inclusive culture.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматривается инклюзивное образование и развитие инклюзивной культуры в обществе. В статье подтверждается важность инклюзивного образования, распространяющего инклюзивность на все слои общества, отвечающего уникальным потребностям каждого человека и видящего значительные изменения в обществе. Также показаны методы и практики, используемые для развития инклюзивной культуры.*

***Ключевые слова:** инклюзивное образование, инклюзивная культура.*

Introduction

In contemporary society, inclusion stands as a fundamental principle of a democratically oriented framework. It addresses one of the most pressing issues of our time: the marginalization of numerous individuals from the economic, social, political, and cultural spheres of their communities. The term "inclusion" has gained prominence alongside the emergence of the notion of "quality education for all." In this context, some scholars (Karagiannis, Stainback & Stainback, 2000) characterize inclusion as a philosophy rooted in the belief that all individuals possess equal rights and opportunities. Inclusiveness is a long-term policy and represents an interdisciplinary approach to organizing the activities of the educational system in all areas.

Inclusion is recognized by the world community as the most humane option for organizing education for people with special needs, therefore this form of education has become one of the leading strategies of global and domestic education policy. A lot of attention is being paid to inclusive education and culture in our country. In particular, in the newly revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (April 30, 2023), inclusive education was given priority and its legal norms were justified. This norm indicated in the encyclopedia of our country indicates that the development of inclusive culture is extremely necessary for the life of the society. The actions taken to create the conceptual foundations of inclusive education will serve the wide spread of inclusive culture in society. Because inclusive education represents a special approach not only to persons with disabilities, but also to subjects of the migration process, representatives of other nationalities, and all learners who have their own identity. The culture of developing an inclusive culture should be based on the principles of humanity, tolerance, and equality, and should ensure the opportunity for education of all young people with inclusion. Inclusive education means a value based on understanding the differences among all

students. Inclusive education is implemented on the basis of recognition of the ability to learn and study of all students with individuality. In the process of inclusive education, the needs of each student are taken into account. As we mentioned above, the process of inclusive education includes not only students with developmental problems, but also children with ethnic identity, individuals who form separate groups according to cultural, social, and age characteristics. The experiences of developed countries in the field of education show that providing education to persons with disabilities, changing the attitude of the state and society towards them in a positive direction, and broadly reflecting the rights of these persons in legislation serve the development of an inclusive culture. Pupils and students who have the uniqueness of those around them change the attitude towards young people in a positive way and expand the scope of dialogue with them. The development of an inclusive culture in society leads to the formation of the experience of treating each person with value based on humanity. In addition, it creates an educational environment without barriers.

Today, teachers are faced with increasingly complex demands and expectations of all other actors in the education profession, parents of students, and the increased number of inclusive students. A particularly sensitive area of inclusive education is educational work in classes that include children with developmental disabilities and learning problems. Supporting the development and academic success of each child in most elementary schools becomes a challenge for teachers due to limited material, spatial and personnel resources, the number and multiple criteria according to which children are categorized as inclusive students, then, numerous reasons for not engaging pedagogical assistants, unplanned professional development of teachers. The attitudes of all actors in the educational process are important for the success of the inclusive process, and the attitudes of teachers are especially important, as they largely determine the success of inclusive practices in school (Avramidis et al., 2000; Hrnjica, 2007; Suzić, 2007). Along with the positive attitude of teachers, previous research confirms the thesis that teachers with concrete experience in implementing an inclusive program and formal competencies acquired through INSET programs expressed significantly more positive attitudes and readiness for further training. It certainly encourages further work on the development of teacher competencies, and at the same time justifies the efforts made so far. Consequently, special attention is paid to the sensitization and professional preparation of teachers to work in an inclusive school, since it is known from practice that the implementation, effects and sustainability of the idea of inclusion crucially depend on the acceptance of inclusion by teachers on the one hand, and inseparably on a properly designed program initial teacher education and then professional training programs (Avramidis et al., 2000; Vujačić, 2005; Subban & Sharma, 2006). Discussion Just as the school is part of the wider society, the culture of the school will reflect those wider social values. The school, as a temporal culture in the sense that its members enter and leave at certain times of the day, and spatially limited or focused around school buildings and grounds, is an arena of negotiation and renegotiation of how these values, assumptions and beliefs are collectively articulated and demonstrated in practice. In this sense, the key to improving the inclusive nature of schools is to reflect on the core values of the school culture and collectively explore, negotiate and experiment with the expression of those values in the school. Although the school organization is influenced by social structures, as an organization it has emergent properties of its own, and is capable of developing in response to its internal dynamics. School culture can change when ambiguities in practice and policy are resolved by confident, forceful, persistent people who succeed in persuading themselves and others to adopt new practices that introduce change. Thus, it is possible for the staff to

reconstruct the organization of the school to meet the needs of the students within it. This will require staff to communicate, problem solve and respect each other and their students. Teachers will have to move beyond the boundaries of traditional school organizations and practices. This means a modern school requires a new approach to leadership and management with the introduction of changes and innovations in material, organizational, programmatic and personnel structures. The implementation of inclusion in education at the level of school practice becomes the daily task of all participants in the educational process at school. The basis of the school's inclusive culture lies in the acceptance and appreciation of diversity as an incentive in work. Inclusion does not mean equalizing all differences, but respecting the differences of individuals. The value of educational inclusion is enabling the acquisition of knowledge, skills and habits for life and work, in accordance with the individual capabilities of individuals, and the acquisition of competences for implementing inclusion at school becomes the basis for modern management of an educational institution. Inclusive culture as a pedagogical dimension of successful educational inclusion leads to the creation of a safe, stimulating community, which accepts and cooperates, in which everyone is respected, which is the foundation for the highest achievements of all community members. It develops common inclusive values that are passed on to all new employees, students, parents and members of the school administration. The principles and values of an inclusive school culture guide decision-making on school policy and every moment of practice in classrooms, so that school development becomes a continuous process.

Types of inclusive culture

The culture of behavior (ethics, behavior) includes the following concepts: feeling high that one is a member of the team, the questions asked are not conflicting, but mutual communication, dialogue, expressing a feeling of openness and benevolence to others. should mean Educational culture: the existence of each student's place in the lesson, a positive approach to each of them, observance of the culture of speaking politely and graciously in every aspect. Caring (accompanying) culture: the presence of an accompanying specialist or peer, the creation of a barrier-free environment. The essence of inclusive culture is as follows: establishment of institutional community; everyone feels welcome and friendly at the institution; peers help each other; warm cooperative relations of educational subjects have been established; all local communities are involved in the process; inclusive values are recognized; hope for the achievements of each student; subjects of the educational process recognize the ideology of inclusion; all students are valued; the team of teachers strives to overcome the obstacles that arise in the process of education and to ensure full participation of all students in the process.

One of the important approaches to the implementation of an inclusive approach and an inclusive culture is the formation of an inclusive culture in the subjects of the educational process and all members of society. This requires the reform of the social consciousness formed among the members of the society in the light of a new approach. Because a stereotype has been formed in people's minds that people with disabilities are not useful for society for a long time. At the same time, there are derogatory attitudes towards people with special needs. Elimination of such views is carried out through the development of an inclusive culture in society. Difficulties in communication and interaction with people with incusia form a negative attitude towards them. As a result, closedness, shyness, and lack of self-confidence are observed in people with inclusion. Therefore, the problem of changing the attitude of people around people with special opportunities is solved by creating an inclusive culture in society. What is an inclusive culture? the question arises. It is known that culture is an indicator achieved as a result of the harmony of education and upbringing. That is why culture finds its expression in the level

of development of society. It is manifested in the creative powers, abilities, and development of a person and is reflected in people's lives and activities. Interpersonal relations are reflected in the values created by them. Accordingly, inclusive culture can be interpreted as follows: Inclusive culture is such a level of social development that it is manifested in tolerance, humanitarianism, tolerance, friendly attitude towards others, cooperation with them and encourages the development of all participants of the educational process. In this process, the value of each person is manifested in the pursuit of common achievements. An inclusive culture is formed when everyone shares inclusive values. Inclusive values are an important component of an inclusive culture. It enriches existing standards and ideals. That is why inclusive culture is an important component of inclusive education. Failure to form an inclusive culture has a negative impact on the educational process. As a result, the possibility of achieving success in the field of inclusive education decreases. It is possible to create favorable conditions for students with special educational needs. However, the human factor cannot be denied. Today, the mass media should combine their capabilities with the officials of educational institutions. Because there is a need to form a culture of treating people with individuality with respect in all members of society. In most cases, they face a difficult psychological and physical situation. Inclusive culture in society not only ensures the success of inclusive education, but also creates favorable conditions for the positive character of relations based on multiculturalism in the society of Uzbekistan. Educators value education based on multiculturalism as an opportunity to prepare the young generation for cultural relations in a multicultural environment. Its main goal is to form a culture of interaction and cooperation among students of different nationalities and faiths. Every person living in the society of Uzbekistan is required to be tolerant, tolerant, respectful towards representatives of other nations and cultures, inclined to live peacefully with them, able to enter into active relations. In order to acquire such skills, it is necessary to master a certain culture. Understanding their values, traditions, customs, and language by developing a valuable, careful, and respectful attitude towards other cultures in students is an important condition for preserving one's national identity and culture. Inclusive education and multicultural education are interconnected. This is reflected in the generality of most ideas and concepts, their goals and tasks. The common aspects of these two directions can be seen in the necessity of tolerance in its implementation. For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of the moral culture of the members of the society. It strengthens the need to form and promote an inclusive culture, create an inclusive cultural space, and create an inclusive worldview in every member of society. Inclusive culture is primarily connected with the concept of multiculturalism. This concept is a part of inclusive education. Inclusion is not only a concept specific to people with health problems, but also a term meaning a culture applied to representatives of other nations. Such individuals differ from each other in their faith, culture, language and outlook.

Respecting the personality of these people and treating them humanely is an important moral quality and indicator of culture for every member of the Uzbek society. Therefore, acquisition of inclusive culture by members of society is a phenomenon that ensures their cultural development for teachers, parents, and students. At the same time, inclusive culture serves the development of a multicultural society and shows that it has an inclusive culture. As a result, in the society of Uzbekistan, acceptance of each person as he is, ending the feeling of anger that he is not like others, expands the possibility of tolerant and tolerant attitude towards others.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, April 30, 2023.
2. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 46 dated 25.01.2024 on measures to improve the system of organizing education and rehabilitation of children with special educational needs.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-134 dated 11.05.2024 on approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education for 2022-2026.
4. Safarova R.G. Inklyuziv ta'lim jamiyatda inklyuziv madaniyatni rivojlantirish omili sifatida. <https://zenodo.org/records/11186721>
5. Avramidis, E., Bayliss, P., & Burden, R. (2000). A Survey into mainstream teachers attitude towards the inclusion of children with special educational needs in the ordinary school in one local education authority. *Educational Psychology*, 20, 191-211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713663717>
6. Безрукова В.С. Основы духовной культуры (энциклопедический словарь педагога). М.: Аспект-Пресс, 2003, с. 594
7. Нигматов З.Г. Формирование поликультурной личности в условиях инклюзивного образования. Сборник научных трудов Международной научно-практической конференции "Поликультурное образовательное пространство Поволжья: пути и формы интеграции" (Казань, КФУ, 1 ноября 2013 г.). - Казань: ИПП КФУ, 2013. - С. 414 - 419.
8. Шеманов А.Ю., Екушевская А.С. Формирование инклюзивной культуры при реализации инклюзивного образования: вызовы и достижения Современная зарубежная психология 2018. Том 7. № 1. С. 29—37. 6. Основы инклюзивной культуры: учебное пособие/Н.А.Борисова и др. Череповецк:ЧГУ, 2021. -214 с.